

Spiritual Satisfaction Becomes a Mutual Need among Individuals

Dinh Van Chien¹, Le Viet Nghi²

¹ University of Social Sciences and Humanities – National University Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

² Dong Nai College of Decorative Arts.

ABSTRACT: The article aims to systematize spiritual life through different needs, thereby clarifying the nature of spiritual life. Spiritual life is a fundamental and essential need, so spiritual wealth is also produced like other goods. It complies with the laws of value, price, competition, supply, and demand. The topic is approached using the human science method to clarify this purpose. Humans are both the subject and the object of perception. Humans are the needs of everyone. The result of this work is to systematize spiritual life, clearly showing that the nature of spiritual life is to produce, exchange, and buy and sell like other goods. It can be concluded that spiritual life is a need, and commodity production is inevitable. The need for goods becomes a human need. Mutual ownership between people is essential. People are produced like other goods. Humans have human needs. Humans are products of each other throughout evolution.

KEYWORDS: People, body, standards, money, satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current context of exchange and integration, it is inevitable. However, different countries, religions, states, companies, and businesses have different standards and interests, making the integration process difficult. Love, truth, justice, standards, and money are everyday satisfactions, but when placed in the relationship between national interests, religion, state, companies, and banks, they are understood very well. Wars and conflicts between countries have ethnic and religious colors; Territorial conquest and imposition of power remain a threat in some regions of the world. Satisfaction as a human being remains a universal need today. Being aware of legitimate satisfaction with full responsibility can avoid possible errors. Spiritual Life Studies provides a multidimensional perspective in finding the value of connection, cooperation, and solidarity between people from families, nations, religions, states, and societies. Different companies and banks have practical implications.

2. Research status of the topic

Many scholars and researchers have approached spiritual life from many different angles. It differs in methodology and perceived objects and is rich and diverse in content, which can be direct or indirect. Published scientific articles include Scientific Life and Methods of Human Cognition. Humans are not only the subject of perception but also the object of perception. The object of perception is not only humans but also nature. Nature and humans have unity in scientific research. Therefore, "natural science includes within itself the science of man just as the science of man includes within itself natural science; it would be a science" (K.Marx and F.Engels, 42, P.179). Under these conditions, "The natural sciences have undertaken a tremendous activity and have accumulated ever-increasing amounts of material. But philosophy remains as foreign to them as to philosophy. Connection Their brief connection with philosophy is a monstrous illusion. The will to combine is present, but the capacity is lacking" (K.Marx and F.Engels, 42, P.178). Humans make natural science lose its abstract materialistic direction, or more accurately, its ideological direction, and become the foundation of science. True human life, but if we "take one basis for life and another basis for science, then from the beginning it is a lie" (K.Marx and F.Engels, 42, P.178 -179). This information is the basis for the author to absorb and inherit to develop his research direction selectively.

3. Research methods

Spiritual life is approached using the methodology of human philosophy and social philosophy, and at the same time, using qualitative methods, general analysis, comparison, and systematization. The primary references are the work of K.Marx and F.Engels and scientific articles published in international journals.

Spiritual Satisfaction Becomes a Mutual Need Among Individuals

4. Discussion and results

4.1. Satisfaction

Nature is man's inorganic body; Humans are the organic body of nature. There is no distinction between humans and nature, but functional differences exist when separated from nature. Human functions are to perceive, create, and produce products to serve life. In survival, maturity has separated humans from nature, leaving themselves behind in the product. Human separation from nature is manifested in a body that performs the function of survival and maintaining the species. Humans and bodies are each other's objects, means, and ends. People use their bodies to create property, and their bodies use people to develop knowledge. Property is outside the body but inside the person. Knowledge is outside the person, but it exists in the body. Humans are connected to the body by mutual satisfaction to form a unified whole.

Human self-awareness is discovered naturally. Self-awareness of hunger and thirst is expressed in awareness of food and water. Satisfaction is the voluntary connection and exchange of products directly. Human life activities differ from animals in that they create satisfaction. When material satisfaction is ignored, spiritual satisfaction appears, and vice versa, or these satisfactions compensate for each other. People are always creative in satisfying different audiences and creating products that meet their needs. The body needs assets to survive; people need knowledge to progress. The way the body uses assets to satisfy itself is shown in driving a car, flying on a plane, answering the phone, eating rice, and drinking water. People, such as children, parents, lay people, clergy, citizens, officials, and business people, use knowledge for satisfaction. Cars, airplanes, telephones, and televisions are assets expressed in terms of money as a standard equivalent of exchange. Children, parents, clergy, officials, and business people are all life knowledge expressed in normative form as an equivalent standard for connection. The exchange and connection between people and money, whether by direct or indirect standards, need to be carefully considered. As human development increases knowledge, the body is secured by increasing assets.

Like other products, the body is perceived, created, and produced, so the direct relationship between products always brings a specific result: the person in that body is created. It is impossible to understand human life without seeing that the object is directly and necessarily related to the body. The human being is perceived, designed, and produced as it becomes a commodity. The body is the means, the person is the end, and vice versa. Just as the body carries awakened senses, humans also carry awakened senses. Human nature is expressed in the body in terms of products, so it is not something abstract or available, but in fact, humans are fully revealed through their actions. Man is expressed through his object in satisfying the object. Without a body, nature is a human abstraction. People have no object to which to react, so suffering appears.

When tools and accessories are repaired and replaced to improve the body's functions, people can express themselves more fully and feel less helpless. Humans have the flaw that knowledge is also created like other goods. Blindness is satisfied by color; people who are deaf or hard of hearing are satisfied by music, and the impaired senses enjoy the knowledge of life in the same way. An agency grows widely whenever knowledge emerges, and the nature of movement becomes a directed development. Creativity is always the product of distorted senses. With spiritual products, spiritual satisfaction appears. With satisfaction, assets can be produced.

However, the spiritual product does not satisfy the universal meaning; it satisfies individual consciousness, so satisfaction is expressed as an individual, a natural person. The difference between individuals is that they need each other in life. Similar individuals do not need each other. When clerics became popular, corpses were buried with cannibals. As mandarinism became widespread, property poverty became legal. When business people become famous, they have so much money that they have no assets to buy. When teachers become popular, knowledge becomes the magic trick of life. Individuals are products produced as commodities to make money. Money as an equivalent is a measure of people being discriminated against.

4.2. General satisfaction

An individual is not a human product; it was not born in the first place, and humans do not need that individual. The individual is not only a manufactured product but also a product of the life designed by that individual. The life of the individual is its product. Everyone is unique; no matter how he creates himself, he makes his products. Isaac Newton discovered the law of universal gravitation, Albert Einstein discovered the theory of relativity, and the production of steam engines, trains, automobiles, and airplanes was primarily the product of individuals. No product belongs to an abstract individual but is always the product of a specific individual. Because each individual is unique, that individual's products are also scarce.

People do not eat and drink knowledge to live, but they can live thanks to knowledge and understanding of food and water. Although knowledge is not for eating, people can live thanks to knowledge and understanding of food and drink. The body can live thanks to the knowledge of choosing particular objects that must exist. People know how to select objects for eternal life and that eternity becomes the reality of human life. Taking actual people as the goal, awareness of the inevitability of life is scientific knowledge. Each individual has a different life, so their scientific knowledge is also different. The richness of scientific knowledge is the richness of personal life. Exchange and connection between individuals is the exchange of scientific knowledge in different fields, fully revealing natural information. Individuals desire each other with all scientific knowledge to create a bond with each other voluntarily, willingly, and freely, which is satisfaction, unity, and diversity. Having scientific knowledge but being unable to satisfy

Spiritual Satisfaction Becomes a Mutual Need Among Individuals

it means that humans exist in abstraction. Different scientific knowledge means different scientists. "Scientific work in response to money makes science not a product of creativity but a product of instincts. Products that serve instincts and create life make science different" (Quoc, N. A., 2024, P.12).

Each person creates personal scientific knowledge and is simultaneously the product of others. Humans are not only the subject providing scientific expertise but also the subject receiving it for mutual improvement. Only do something with scientific knowledge; only do things that do not fully reveal your scientific knowledge. The social meaning is to reprimand and criticize those who are capable but do not fully demonstrate scientific knowledge and do not require those without scientific knowledge to contribute to society. Learn about life and absorb new scientific knowledge. Good standards are also an inevitable product of each specific individual. Hunger, illness, and death are products of each individual, so they are considered everyday misfortunes of the human condition. Not realizing that hunger, illness, and death are everyday misfortunes means not having compassion for the hungry, compassion for the sick, or sadness for the dead. When everyone acknowledges human misfortunes, mutual love between people becomes spiritual satisfaction. "It is generally the mother who naturally and practically remains the biggest source of love, guidance, care, supervision, inspiration, and motivation to the child" (Ghulam Fatima, Farooq Tanwir, Ashfaq Ahmad Mann and Abdul Saboor, 2009, P.100). The product of an individual's universal response is that it is socialized. The product is no longer personal but social when universal satisfaction is realized. The laws of universal gravitation, the theory of relativity, and the production of airplanes and telephones are not universal and cannot be socialized.

That socialization product belongs to talented individuals and society. Scientific knowledge and assets have become so widespread that anyone can do it, and there is no need for human standards because everyone is the same. Popularly updated scientific knowledge becomes a connecting link between people. Any scientific knowledge that meets real life is valuable. The value of scientific knowledge becomes the value of the person who implements it. Correct implementation of scientific knowledge will create a vivid reality, revealing the inevitability of nature. Science becomes a commodity. "Science is a commodity that entrepreneurs speculate on, trade, and make a profit. Having science means having money, and having money means having power. The power of money becomes the power of science. Science is the life of people with money. Money becomes the life of science" (Quoc, N. A., 2024, P.15-16).

The same universal human being exists in different bodies; Discrimination between bodies becomes discrimination between people. Therefore, standards do not become a measure of human value. Norms do not require everyone to perform the same behavior but only apply to people who behave differently. The meaning of the standard is to make individuals more human, to return the individual to being human, and to share the exact nature of development. The standard is one species; Connections between individuals are formed, and standards become shared satisfaction. The standard of not becoming a person becomes meaningless. But being human has become so common that people with similar standards have become redundant.

Standards are the product of talented individuals. When talent appears, scientific knowledge is discovered, standards are formed, and a widely recognized standard is called instinct. Standards are products of individuals, so standards exist not only in that individual but also in those with the standards. People enjoy art and enjoy those standards. Enjoy standard behaviors such as watching magic tricks, circuses, dancing, and music. Norms become pleasing, so an individual who behaves according to norms can live as a magician, circus performer, dancer, or singer. A standard that does not give life is a standard that becomes meaningless behavior. But any standard of ability to make a living becomes satisfactory. With hot growth and inflation of standards, lies emerge. The lie was discovered and became a laughing stock to the world. A lie that goes undetected is not a lie. Deception only exists among people with standards, but people with standards may not cheat. Standards become objects of falsehood. Standards cover up falsehood, so standards that create falsehood are constantly increasing. When lies appear, the truth still exists, distorting the relationships between such people. Truth becomes a common spiritual satisfaction. Knowledge of life norms such as traditions, canons, and laws became widespread. It is not a living reality, so it is no longer scientific knowledge. Just as human connection through norms increases dishonesty, human exchange through money also increases injustice. Money and standards are scarce, so cash and standards give people different satisfaction levels. "Scientists live by scientific products. The scientific research profession is a scientist. Science is a commodity. A scientist's effort, intelligence, and talent are measured in money. The right to life is money" (Quoc, N. A. 2024, P.10).

4.3. Production of spiritual goods

When money becomes the common purpose of exchange, bodies, knowledge, standards, and assets are all commodities. Through knowledge, the individual becomes the subject of the body. The body contains people with different organs. Each agency has various functions that become cooperation between people. Human shortcomings are loneliness, unconsciousness, helplessness, and unhappiness expressed in the solidarity between people. This person is the ability and need of the other person.

People become objects for mutual enjoyment and mutual education, which is the process of life being changed by knowledge of life. Individuals are creative and valuable subjects, which can be replicated and become social values. On the contrary, society attracts backward individuals, bringing no benefit from their backward condition. Individuals are products of social circumstances. Life is not only regulated by standards but also by the exchange of money. Money is the goal, so no matter how much money a

Spiritual Satisfaction Becomes a Mutual Need Among Individuals

person has, it is noble. When money loses value, people who have money also lose value. Money is the means; Money can be bought and sold like any other commodity. Satisfaction of standards and scarcity of money were the prevailing spirit. A standard change is that money appears again like that. Individuals who create scarce spiritual wealth will become wealthy in money and normative desires. “Money becomes indispensable in social life. Standard selling is buying work to make money. Social life has the instincts of a species with different standards and funds” (Quoc, N. A. , Y, N. V. , & Giau, H. V. , 2024, P.4982).

Individuals, bodies, knowledge, assets, standards, and money are unified, so exchanging assets, knowledge, money, and standards is an exchange between individuals. Individuals are particular goods, spiritual goods. Spiritual goods are produced equally, and pleasing everyone is business. Business is effective when goods are scarce and unique but must serve social needs. Trading in spiritual goods is also economically practical. If you want to do business and produce spiritual goods effectively, the principle is to speculate or monopolize the production of scarce spiritual goods to satisfy socialized needs.

The ability to speculate and monopolize each individual is inevitable, demonstrating talent. The individual is an exclusive product, so the individual is scarce, and the individual's product is also scarce. Exchanges and purchases of expertise and assets between individuals become goods exchanged and sold on the market. Personal labor assets sold on the market have less economic efficiency than professional, mass-produced goods with supporting machinery, science, and technology—individuals who do business effectively and exploit exclusive products on their bodies. The body is expressed through circus, magic, dancing, singing, gymnastics, sports, and martial arts to exchange, buy, and sell to make a profit.

The body plays a unique role through actions of joy, anger, love, and hate, like a stage magic trick performed in daily life, making life bitter and colorful. Organs, cosmetic surgery, deformities, knowledge, prestige, honor, standards, conscience, labor, and behavior contained in the body are all bought and sold. Love, eternal happiness, justice, truth, standards, and money are good when the goal and the means to achieve happiness differ. “Therefore, this particular form of social well-being is associated with increased social interaction and overall contentment” (Wan Yuwen, Liang Jiang, 2023, P.727). Use individuals to exchange, buy, and sell effectively, with low production costs, and meet the richness and diversity of society.

Television, the internet, machines, equipment, and accessories were born to respond to the spirit, but loneliness, unconsciousness, helplessness, and unhappiness appeared. When it is an act of helping, living happily, increasing longevity, and being respected. Recognizing people with each other is always the purpose of life. Individuals still need each other worldwide, so there is nothing more beautiful, noble, and joyful than real people together. But people have sex with each other not to eat, drink, or breathe but to satisfy each other with all the knowledge of life. Each individual is a creative product, designing their life with life knowledge, but trading on the market becomes a spiritual commodity. Investing in yourself with your unique and exclusive nature in business to get rich is an inevitable trend. Without the spirit of universal humanity, investing in people will not bring economic efficiency. Liver and kidney replacement: Just like buying and selling assets, money, knowledge, buying and selling people, standards, and making money on the body are all the same.

Without this exchange, assets, knowledge, standards, and money would not exist. Human nature is not revealed, and economic, social, and technological development does not appear. Preserved, hoarded, and accumulated assets, knowledge, standards, and money have become increasingly common in production and consumption, making them scarce and individual. This scarcity makes humans truly valuable. Wealth, knowledge, standards, and money are all human. People are necessary for assets, knowledge, money, and standards to be meaningful. Investing in people is investing in development. People are genuinely spiritual goods. The rich and aristocratic could no longer sell individual parts to regular customers. “Customers can move back and forth between stages, and the time it takes for a customer to go through the funnel can vary greatly” (Hadzhi, K. M., Vali, G. X., Viladdin, M. A., Cemil, K. I., Ali, Y. S., Fizuli, H. Z., & Tahir, P. A., 2024, P.14). All can trade goods, rich, poor, noble and humble in the market, becoming the same merchants but with differences in exclusivity in trading. In conditions of scarce means of production and a large population, the tendency to express human nature is becoming increasingly prosperous. Creativity takes satisfaction as its direct object in creating a natural human being. When real people become living subjects of each other in appropriating property, laziness, theft, robbery, smuggling, tax evasion, corruption, bribery, knowledge trafficking, and purchasing standards occur.

You see money as the counterpart to wealth, and making a living becomes the goal of making money. There are many ways to make money with purpose, but one of the most effective ways to run a business is to invest in real people. People who know how to invest in themselves from the beginning are shown in family heads, religious leaders, state leaders, and company directors. Patriarchs, patriarchs, leaders, and directors lived their lives caring for the weak, helping the poor, and creating rich and talented people. The talent of patriarchs, religious leaders, leaders, and directors lies in the exchange and connection between different people, redistributing products to satisfy the majority. Patriarchs, patriarchs, leaders, and directors all turned the famous spirit of the times into reality, making loneliness, unconsciousness, helplessness, and unhappiness a thing of the past.

Life knowledge about patriarchs, religious leaders, leaders, and managers is socialized into specific historical norms. Spouses, children, parents, and grandparents are bound together by life and family. Clergy are bound together by religion, and the state binds cadres together. Companies connect business people. Unassociated species also do not appear. When species appeared, they existed in family members, clergy, officials, and business people. Human nature exists in specific social situations within the species and is a synthesis of those situations. Workers live by their brains and hands, while family members, clergy, officials, and business people

Spiritual Satisfaction Becomes a Mutual Need Among Individuals

live by species. Animals are the means of living for family members, clergy, officials, and business people. The minds and hands of workers are the goods of the species, the goods of patriarchs, clergy, officials, and business people. Patriarchs, religious leaders, leaders, and administrators are unique phenomena of living reality, so the rest of society has everyday spirituality.

No matter how scarce individuals are compared to society, fake people still appear. Artificially created people appear in a division that includes patriarchs, clerics, officials, and business people. When patriarchs, clergy, officials, and business people increased and inflation became common, bad habits of patriarchs, clergy, officials, and business people appeared. Injustice among honest workers also occurs when the bad habits of patriarchs, clergy, officials, and businesspeople appear rampant.

Each individual's product is necessarily unique; no matter how rich the differences between individuals are, their products are also brilliant and diverse. Exchange between products is inevitable, but because of financial prosperity, business people believe in fairness and honesty of money as equivalent standards in exchange. Commodities: Real people can sell their body parts; They have freedom, so freedom is an essential condition for real people to buy and sell themselves without violating tradition, canon law, and law. Education about love, justice, truth, gratitude, hope, promises, the afterlife, standards, law, and money, but when placed in the relationship between species, that value becomes a chaotic, contradictory dream, so real people become its victims. "The goal is to return these individuals to the community and have them accepted as human beings rather than judging them for their past actions" (Adnan, M., Musyafak, N., Setiyono, B., & Amaliyah, A., 2024, P.11).

Money and standards bring life knowledge to develop people, but hypocrisy appears in patriarchs, priests, officials, and business people when it becomes a goal. Live with all the responsibilities of a human being: no more comparisons, calculating truth and falsehood, justice and injustice, equality in exchange, and connecting all naturally produced products freely, voluntarily, and not for profit. Each human being not only exists in the natural world but is also governed by species. Competition between species is inevitable in the process of perfecting human nature. Similar to the way the market economy is eliminating counterfeit goods, poor quality goods, and species markets, education is also removing bad habits of patriarchy, clergy, officials, business people, and teachers. When the lies of patriarchs, clergy, officials, business people, and teachers are eliminated, human nature is fully expressed in the life activities of real people with functions and tasks—the process of social division of labor.

5. CONCLUSION

Through the discussion and results achieved, I can draw the following conclusion.

Humans and nature merge into one; there is no distinction. When humans separate from nature, they become independent subjects. Individuals are each other's abilities and needs. People become a need of society.

Two, people are each other's abilities and needs. Life is about mutual satisfaction. Human satisfaction with the outside world becomes the instinct of animals. Loneliness and coldness are determined by money and standards. People become different types of goods.

Third, people are goods produced as different types of goods. Each person sells himself to get money, making himself a particular commodity with personality. All goods become redundant; human goods become scarce. Humans are the value and need of all.

REFERENCES

- 1) New Testament Bible, Religion Publishing House, Hanoi, 2012.
- 2) K.Marx and F.Engels, Complete Volume, Volume 42, National political publisher, Hanoi, 2000.
- 3) Quoc, N. A. (2024). SCIENTIFIC LIFE. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 12(6), e3734. <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v12i6.3734>
- 4) Hadzhi, K. M., Vali, G. X., Viladdin, M. A., Cemil, K. I., Ali, Y. S., Fizuli, H. Z., & Tahir, P. A. (2024). MARKETING STRATEGY AS A KEY FACTOR OF INNOVATIVE PRODUCTS' MARKET DEVELOPMENT. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 12(7), e3755. <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v12i7.3755D>
- 5) Adnan, M., Musyafak, N., Setiyono, B., & Amaliyah, A. (2024). NAVIGATING THE JOURNEY TO PEACE: A STUDY OF ASSIMILATION AND REINTEGRATION OF EX-OFFENDERS OF TERRORISM. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 12(6), e3691. <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v12i6.3691>.
- 6) Wan Yuwen, Liang Jiang (2023). To Compare the Development of Social Relationships Between Individuals Who Perform and Who Do Not Perform Leisure Sports Activities and the Impact of Leisure Sports Activities on Social Health. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, E-ISSN: 2221-7630; P-ISSN: 1727-4915, 21(2): 716-731. www.pjlss.edu.pk <https://doi.org/10.57239/PJLSS-2023-21.2.0014>
- 7) Ghulam Fatima, Farooq Tanwir, Ashfaq Ahmad Mann and Abdul Saboor (2009). Tracing the Impact of Socio-Economic Status of Parents on Personality Formation of Children. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, E-ISSN: 2221-7630; P-ISSN: 1727-4915, Pak. j. life soc. Sci. (2009), 7(1): 98-100.
- 8) Quoc, N. A. ., Y, N. V. ., & Giao, H. V. ., (2024). Personal Freedom Become Social Responsibility. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, E-ISSN: 2221-7630; P-ISSN: 1727-4915, Pak. j. life soc. Sci. (2009), 7(1): P.4977-4983. https://www.pjlss.edu.pk/pdf_files/2024_1/4977-4983.pdf